

Do Public and Private Banks Value ESG Differently- An Empirical Analysis from India

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance performance on the financial outcomes of selected Indian private and public sector banks, using Return on Assets and Return on Equity as dependent variable . Data was employed from CRISIL,both public and private sector banks, and the major variables were data was sourced from the screener and analysed through the lenses of Stakeholder Theory, Legitimacy Theory, Resource-Based View, Institutional Theory, and Signalling Theory.Findings of the study suggest that while governance and environmental factors are well-developed, the social dimension remains underdeveloped.ESG rating does not show a strong short term indicator of financial performance moreover, it had hold an potential for long-term risk transfer and in benefiting the stakeholder trust.Ownership had as a moderating variable, with private banks leveraging ESG for market differentiation and public banks focusing on social impact.The study highlights the need for enhanced ESG disclosure aligned with global standards and recommends incorporating non-financial key performance indicator for better transparency. It also develops the future research using panel data methods and structural equation modelling to uncover causal pathways. Overall, ESG integration should be viewed not only as a compliance tool but as a strategic driver of sustainable banking and long-term value creation in the Indian context.

I.INTRODUCTION

In recent years,Environmental,Social and Governance considerations have emerged as critical benchmarks for evaluating the sustainable performance and ethical consideration of financial institutions the banking sector has grown through growing regulatory and shifting investor preferences with the prioritization of the sustainability and long-term value creation of the banks this shift of ESG strategic discourse in banking, especially in economies navigating developmental and regulatory transitions like India.

Despite its growing significance empirical evidence on the influence of ESG performance on the financial outcomes of Indian banks remains very limited .Existing literature is highly concentrated in developed markets, with most studies relying on aggregate ESG indices rather than distributing the individual components of ESG.Furthermore,there is a distinct lack of comparative analysis between public and private sector banks, especially in terms of key profitability indicators such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE).

This gap in literature becomes more crucial when it has an consideration of that ownership component public and private can shape institutional preferences, stakeholder expectations, and strategic approaches to ESG integration.While developed economies have offered insights into ESG-financial performance linkages, Indian banks operate in a unique regulatory, economic, and social context that warrants an independent investigation, past studies have underexplored the moderation effect of ownership on the ESG-financial performance nexus,which this research aims to address.

In this study will contribute for both academic discourse and policy formulation by analyzing the individual components of ESG ratings on ROA and ROE and by comparing how public and private sector banks respond to ESG dimensions. These are based on the Stakeholder Theory,Resource-Based View ,Institutional Theory

,Signalling Theory and Legitimacy Theory. This research aims to decode whether ESG factors translate into tangible financial performance and how this relationship by bank ownership structure is addressed these research gaps the study will to provide enhanced insights into how Indian banks can align profitability with sustainability goals, offering value to investors, regulators, and society at large.

II.LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 THEORETICAL OVERVIEW

To analyze the influence of ESG ratings on the financial performance of Indian banks, this study draws on a multi-theoretical framework that includes Stakeholder Theory (Boateng et al., 2025; Cantero-Saiz et al., 2024; Dogan Basar et al., 2025; Dragomir et al., 2022; El Khoury et al., 2023; Gutiérrez-Ponce & Wibowo, 2023; Jaiwani & Gopalkrishnan, 2023; Maztoul, 2025; Prasad & Mondal, 2025), Resource-Based View (RBV)(Boateng et al., 2025; Dragomir et al., 2022), Legitimacy Theory(Boateng et al., 2025; Gutiérrez-Ponce & Wibowo, 2023),Signaling Theory(Prasad & Mondal, 2025) and Institutional Theory.The Stakeholder Theory provides a base for understanding how bank ESG performance addresses the expectations of stakeholders which can enhance financial outcomes such as Return on Assets and Return on Equity, aligning with the first objective.RBV supports the idea that ESG practices represent intangible management of resources that contribute to a bank's competitive advantage and improved performance. The second objective which aims to analyse the individual impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance scores on ROA and ROE, is grounded in both RBV and Legitimacy Theory each ESG pillar contributes uniquely to a bank resource and societal acceptance and which influencing financial metrics differently.Signalling Theory is particularly relevant in explaining how ESG disclosures act as indicators of sound risk management and ethical governance thereby attracting investors and improving performance.For the third and fourth objectives comparing public and private sector banks and testing moderating role of ownership,Institutional Theory plays a key role.

It explains how regulatory, normative, and cultural pressures influence ESG adoption differently across ownership types like public sector banks may adopt ESG under government mandates, whereas private banks do it for the strategic positioning.Both together, Collectively these theories provide an excellent framework that justifies the exploration of ESG's impact on bank performance in the Indian context.

2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL RATINGS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF THE BANKS

The relationship between environmental ratings and financial performance is very difficultly sorted and increased recongnation where as most studies suggest a positive correlation between them though the strength of this link varies by industry, region, and specific environmental practices.In case of the **European food industry**, firms with higher ESG ratings modestly better financial outcomes, such as ROA and ROE said by (Sandberg et al., 2022). **Industry benchmarking** reveals that best class of environmental performers often achieve higher financial performance than their peers the efforts were made by (Gull et al., 2022). The **microfinance sector** institutions with environmental policies report better returns and lower costs (Beisland et al., 2022).In **China** environmental regulations initially reduce financial performance due to added costs which lead to long-term gains through improved efficiency and green innovation in (Liu et al., 2022; Lee, 2020).Research also shows that **environmental practices and management processes** are strongly linked to financial performance by (Delmas et al., 2013).Sector-specific approaches such as in **mining and metals**,underscore the need for customised strategies by (Yeomans, 2004).Finally while environmental responsibility is to benefit financial performance and its has various **impacts**.For instance

environmental practices have a stronger influence in developing countries as compared to developed nations and its disclosure does not guarantee financial benefits by (Guastella et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2022). From this we can acquire two hypothesis **H1a**: Environmental ratings have a significant positive influence on ROA of banks. And **H1b**: Environmental ratings have a significant positive influence on ROE of banks.

2.3 SOCIAL RATINGS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF THE BANKS

The connection with social ratings and financial performance is very difficult and there is increased and relevant in modern investment analysis. Social ratings often part of broader ESG, influence financial outcomes through consumer trust, investor preferences and risk mitigation. Research shows a positive relationship between corporate social performance and financial outcomes. Firms with good social practices tend to perform better both in the short and long term, as good management enhances CSP and boosts returns (Waddock & Graves, 1997). In Korean firms CSR disclosure improves financial performance with reputation playing a mediating role by (Kim, 2023). Socially responsible investing especially strategies using high social ratings can generate significant abnormal returns up to 8.7% annually when applying a the best class approach by (Kempf & Osthoff, 2007). This shows that integrating social ratings into investment decisions can be financially beneficial. Analysts once viewed high CSR scores typically but as stakeholder awareness grew, they began offering more favourable recommendations for socially responsible firms (Ioannou & Serafeim, 2015). This shift reflects a broader recognition of social performance as a driver of financial value. Despite the positive links, concerns remain. Some socially rated indices include controversial firms, questioning rating credibility (Arribas et al., 2019). Additionally, higher ESG ratings can sometimes increase investor uncertainty and perceived risk, especially when corporate and investor goals misalign (Landi et al., 2022). **H2a**: Social ratings have a significant positive influence on ROA of banks. And **H2b**: Social ratings have a significant positive influence on ROE of banks.

2.4 GOVERNANCE RATINGS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE

The link between governance ratings and financial performance is very difficult but increasingly recognised as very crucial for sustainable success. Governance as a key pillar of ESG which contributes to a firm financial health though it has an high impact on industry, region and firm specific practices the studies confirm that there is an strong positive association between corporate governance and financial performance indicators such as ROA and ROE. European firms with high conditioned governance structures which shows improved financial outcomes by (Siminica et al., 2019). In China ESG performance including governance enhanced financial results specifically when linked to green innovation which is said by (Zheng et al., 2022). Board characteristics also matter: longer board tenure and greater female representation were associated with improved returns in South Africa, Nigeria, and Ghana (Bein, 2023). The quality of internal controls can significantly moderate the governance-performance link. Weak internal controls, as observed in French firms, undermine the financial benefits of high ESG scores (Boulhaga et al., 2022). Governance impacts also vary across sectors and countries for example, differing results in the banking sectors of Romania and Italy by (Benvenuto et al., 2021). However ESG engagement is especially impactful during the growth stage of a company's life cycle by (Gao et al., 2023). Despite the overall positive link, challenges remain. Inconsistent governance standards across regions complicate global comparisons (Khanna, 2009). Additionally the ESG efforts are perceived as superficial or misaligned with core strategy, they can increase investor scepticism and risk by (Landi et al., 2022). These factors highlight the need for genuine, context-specific governance strategies. **H3a**: Governance ratings have a significant positive influence on ROA of banks and **H3b**: Governance ratings have a significant positive influence on ROE of banks.

2.5 ESG AND BANK STABILITY

The connection between Environmental, Social and Governance strategies and bank stability has gained important attention in recent years, especially for their role during periods of financial expectation the ESG practices are increasingly absorbed as tools to transfer risks and enhance the resilience of financial institutions. A study on European banks from 2005 to 2017 found that higher ESG scores were associated with reduced bank fragility during times of financial distress with the stabilizing effect becoming more pronounced in banks with a longer history of ESG disclosures were said by (Chiaromonte et al., 2021, Lupu et al., 2022) using systemic risk measures such as Expected Shortfall of MES & CoVaR and confirming that ESG scores will have more influence in financial stability in the European banking sector. The impact of individual ESG pillars further reveals the nuanced ways in which sustainability practices affect banks.

Environmental and social (ES) activities help reduce credit and liquidity risks by building stakeholder trust and fostering a stakeholder-centric culture, especially during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic (Li et al., 2022). In the context of US banks the relationship between ESG and market value is nonlinear relationship with the Social and environmental score which shows an inverted U shaped indicating that the helps of ESG investments vary with intensity and focus with as said by (Ersoy et al., 2022). At a systemic level of ESG performance has been linked to lower risk and reduced contribution to financial system instability quoted in the (Scholtens and Klooster 2019) argue that higher sustainability scores will increase the financial stability of the company or firms the underscoring the relevance of ESG in risk management and policy formulation. Regional dynamics also influence ESG effectiveness. China state-owned banks which lead to the in ESG adoption due to greater regulatory pressure and competitive market structures (Chiu, 2022). In contrast, Indonesian banks exhibit a generally negative relationship between overall ESG performance and financial indicators like Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE), although the social pillar positively influences these metrics (Gutiérrez-Ponce & Wibowo, 2023).

2.6 ESG and Financial Performance

The relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) activities and financial performance is intricate and context-dependent, reflecting a range of positive, negative, and mixed outcomes across different industries and geographies. Increasingly, ESG practices are seen as strategic imperatives, with the potential to influence both short-term financial results and long-term value creation. Moreover their impact is far from uniform in the European food industry has higher ESG ratings are modestly impacted on improved financial outcomes such as Return on Assets and Return on Equity the idea of ESG integration can be beneficial told by (Sandberg et al., 2022). Similarly among small and medium-sized manufacturers in China, ESG efforts positively influence financial performance, mediated by enhancements in non-financial performance (Liu et al., 2022). The China Growth Enterprise Market green innovation and ESG performance both positively affect financial outcomes with ESG playing a mediating role which suggest that the innovation of the firms strengthens the financial value of and its sustainability practices which was said by (Zheng et al., 2022). Counterly not all studies report a uniformly positive relationship between the ESG and financial performance. The Indonesian banks has an ESG activities are generally negatively correlated with ROA, ROE, and Tobin's Q. Nevertheless, the social component of ESG contributes positively to ROA and ROE, while governance practices negatively influence Tobin's Q, indicating component-specific effects (Gutiérrez-Ponce & Wibowo, 2023). Complexity is taken care by China's Yangtze River Delta, where environmental actions reduce financial performance, but governance practices enhance it, revealing a mixed pattern of influence (Liu et al., 2022). Furthermore, an inverted U-shaped relationship identified in Taiwanese firms indicates that while ESG investment initially boosts financial performance, excessive engagement may lead to diminishing returns, emphasizing the importance of balance in ESG strategy (Teng et al., 2022). Adding to this complexity, several studies emphasise the role of mediating and moderating variables. Innovation capacity of the mediating role, particularly in innovation-intensive firms, where ESG investments can lead to better financial performance through enhanced product or process innovation (Doni, 2023; Liu et al., 2022). In the other hand the institutional context the including regulatory frameworks and consumer expectations moderates the ESG performance linkage which influencing ESG initiatives are financially rewarded. Internal factors like Total Quality Management practices also shape this relationship which is affecting how ESG initiatives are implemented and perceived thereby altering their financial implications induced by (Chams et al., 2021).

H4: Comparative study of Environmental Social Governance impact on the financial performance of private sector banks and public sector banks

II. Research methodology

This study follows the quantitative research methodology to analyze the relationship between Environmental, Social and Governance scores and financial performance of Indian private and public sector banks, with an mediating variable as ownership structures based on the multiple theoretical perspectives like Stakeholder Theory, Resource-Based View, Signaling Theory, Legitimacy Theory, and Institutional Theory which providing a lens through which ESG scores and financial outcomes can be interpreted. The study relies entirely on secondary data obtained from CRISIL, a reputed Indian credit rating agency. The dataset includes the latest ESG scores like E- Score, S-score, G- Score and the combined score of ESG and the dependent variables Return on Assets, Return on Equity (ROE) for 18 Indian private and public sector banks. The data is cross-sectional, representing a snapshot for the financial year 2023–2024. The sample was

selected using purposive sampling, ensuring inclusion of banks with complete and reliable data. The four main objectives: (1) to examine the influence of overall ESG ratings on the financial performance (ROA and ROE) of Indian banks; (2) to analyze the individual effects of environmental, social, and governance components on financial performance; (3) to compare ESG-performance relationships across public and private banks; and (4) to identify whether ownership moderates the ESG-financial performance nexus. The data analysis will proceed in multiple stages. First descriptive statistics will be computed to summarise ESG and financial indicators. Second, correlation analysis will be used to evaluate linear relationships between ESG components and financial performance. Third, multiple linear regression analysis will assess the impact of each ESG dimension on ROA and ROE. To analyze moderation effects, interaction terms between ESG scores and ownership type will be included in the regression models and finally, the Descriptive of mean will be conducted to assess whether public and private banks differ significantly in ESG scores and financial metrics. All statistical analyses will be conducted using software Jamovi while Excel will be used for data cleaning. Since the data is collected from a recognized and publicly accessible source (CRISIL), ethical risks are minimal. Proper citations and acknowledgement of data sources will be maintained throughout the research.

III. Analysis

Table no 3.1 showing Descriptive statistics

	Environment Score	Social Score	Governance Score	ESG Score	ROA	ROE
N	18	18	18	18	18	18
Kurtosis	0.032	-0.506	-1.68	-0.222	0.676	-0.02
Maximum	70	68	77	71	2.34	22.8
Mean	56	62	68	63	1.2	13
Median	57	62	68	63	1.1	13
Minimum	47	53	61	55	0.5	4.73
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Skewness	0.491	-0.26	0.0846	0.0124	0.822	-0.063
Standard deviation	6.02	4.24	6.01	4.09	0.474	4.68
Std. error kurtosis	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.04
Std. error skewness	0.536	0.536	0.536	0.536	0.536	0.536
Variance	36.2	17.9	36.1	16.7	0.23	21.9

From the above table mentioned ESG scores of Indian private and public sector banks shows balanced performance across the three different dimensions Environment, Social, and Governance. The mean scores indicate that Governance is the highest rated mean is 68.2, Social 61.8 and Environment 56.2. This suggests that Indian private and public sector banks are placing more emphasis on governance frameworks compared to other two. The standard deviations are moderate, with the social score being the most consistent SD = 4.24 while Environment and Governance scores show slightly more variability which around 6. All ESG components exhibit near normal distribution with skewness values close to zero. Moreover the Environment score shows a mild positive skew, indicating a few banks have higher environmental scores, while Social is slightly negatively skewed. Governance has the lowest kurtosis that is -1.68, suggesting a relatively flat distribution with fewer extreme values. The financial performance the average Return on Assets ROA is 1.17% and Return on Equity is 13.1%, both indicating healthy profitability levels typical for Indian private and public banking institutions. ROA displays a positive skew with 0.822, hinting that a few banks outperform significantly in terms of asset efficiency. ROE is nearly symmetrically distributed skewness ≈ -0.06 and shows modest variability SD is 4.68.

0.49). Additionally it shows a weak, negative and statistically insignificant relationship with ROA that is $r = -0.216$ and $p = 0.39$ which highlighting its less impact on financial performance in this dataset.

Governance Score stands out as a critical driver, showing a very strong and significant correlation with the overall ESG Score ($r = 0.874$, $p < .001$), reflecting that robust governance practices are central to ESG performance. Moderate and significant correlation with the Environmental Score, further establishes the interlinkages between good governance and environmental responsibility. Moreover its correlation with ROA is very weak and statistically insignificant results of $r = 0.092$ and $p = 0.717$ which suggests that superior governance may not directly improve short-term financial performance. The overall ESG Score demonstrates a strong correlation with both the Environmental and Governance Scores, confirming that these two components heavily influence composite ESG ratings. The correlation between ESG Score and ROA is less and non statistically significant $r = 0.052$ and $p = 0.837$ which indicates that higher ESG scores do not improve the result in improved financial performance in terms of ROA within the sample taken. This could be attributed to the short term nature of ROA very limited sample size. Overall while the ESG framework shows internal consistency particularly between environment and governance it has direct financial implications, especially concerning ROA, that remain unsubstantiated in this analysis.

Hypothesis testing

Table no 3.3

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures		
Model	R	R ²
1	0.239	0.0571

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=18

Table no 3.4

Model Coefficients - ROA				
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	2.0957	2.496	0.84	0.416
Environment Score	-0.0433	0.248	-0.175	0.864
Social Score	-0.0544	0.168	-0.324	0.751
Governance Score	-0.0411	0.248	-0.166	0.871
ESG Score	0.1227	0.655	0.187	0.854

The linear regression analysis analyzes the impact of individual ESG components Environment, Social and Governance scores as well as the combined ESG score on Return on Assets ROA, using a sample size of 18 observations of both private and public sector banks. The model reveals a very weak explanatory power, with an R-value of 0.239 and an R² of just 0.0571 which indicating that only 5.7% of the difference in ROA by the ESG variables. This suggests that ESG factors does not have influence financial performance which is measured by ROA in the given dataset.

ESG individual coefficients and none of the predictors show statistical importance. The Environment Score has a negative coefficient of -0.0433 with a high p-value of 0.864 which indicates no meaningful impact on ROA. Social Score with -0.0544 and $p = 0.751$ and Governance Score is -0.0411 and p value is 0.871 also show negative but non-significant relationships. Overall ESG Score which has a positive coefficient of 0.1227 is not statistically significant with the p is 0.854. The model is 2.0957, but with a p-value of 0.416 also not significant.

In summary the regression model confirms that neither the individual ESG components nor the overall ESG Score have a statistically significant results on ROA. The very low R² value further tells us that ESG factors are poor predictors of financial performance in this context. These results align with the very nascent stage of correlation analysis and suggest that ESG performance will not directly contribute to short-term financial gains particularly in terms of ROA possibly due to the limited sample size or other unobserved variables.

Objective :- 3 To compare the effect of ESG ratings on financial performance between public sector banks and private sector banks

Table no 3.5

Linear Regression

Model Fit Measures

Model	R	R ²
1	0.417	0.174

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=18

Table no 3.6

Model Coefficients - ROE

Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p
Intercept	11.51	23.03	0.5	0.625
Environment Score	-2.29	2.28	-1.003	0.334
Social Score	-1.19	1.55	-0.768	0.456
Governance Score	-1.94	2.29	-0.848	0.412
ESG Score	5.38	6.05	0.889	0.39

The linear regression analysis assessing the impact of ESG components and the overall ESG score on Return on Equity which yields modest explanatory power. The model shows a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.417 and an R² value of 0.174, meaning that approximately 17.4% of the variation in ROE can be explained by the ESG-related predictors. R² is slightly higher than that observed in the ROA model it is still considered to be very low which indicating that ESG scores do not strongly predict ROE in this context.

Examining the individual parameters, none of these are statistically significant. The Environmental Score has a negative coefficient of -2.29 and the p value of 0.334 suggesting a negative but insignificant impact on ROE. The Social Score of -1.19 with the p value of 0.456 and Governance Score of -1.94, p value of 0.412 also show negative and non-significant relationship with ROE. The overall ESG Score, despite having a positive coefficient of 5.38, is not statistically significant either (p = 0.390). The intercept of the model stands at 11.51 with a p-value of 0.625, indicating it too lacks statistical relevance.

Regression results indicate that neither the individual ESG components nor the combined ESG Score have a significant influence on ROE. While the model explains slightly more fluctuations in terms of ROE than in ROA the results are statistically insignificant across all predictors. This suggests that ESG performance, whether in environmental, social or governance aspects does not have a strong and direct impact on short-term financial performance in terms of equity returns within the analyzed sample. A larger sample size or the inclusion of additional control variables may be necessary for more conclusive insights

Objective :-4 To identify whether ownership moderates the ESG–financial performance relationship

Table no 3.7

ANOVA Omnibus tests					
	SS	df	F	p	η ² p
Model	0.6774	3	1.004	0.42	0.177
OWNERSHI P	0.6669	2	1.484	0.26	0.175
ESG Score	0.083	1	0.369	0.553	0.026
Residuals	3.1469	14			
Total	3.8242	17			

Fixed Effects Parameter Estimates		
		95% Confidence

Names	Effect	Estimate	SE	Interval		β	df	t	p
				Lower	Upper				
(Intercept)	(Intercept)	1.0204	0.1771	0.64	1.4002	0	14	5.761	<.001
OWNERSHIP1	02-Jan	-0.7833	0.5073	-1.871	0.3048	-1.651	14	-1.544	0.145
OWNERSHIP2	0 - 1	-0.3842	0.337	-1.107	0.3386	-0.81	14	-1.14	0.273
ESG Score	ESG Score	-0.0251	0.0413	-0.114	0.0635	-0.216	14	-0.608	0.553

The ANOVA omnibus test results suggest that the model which includes ownership as an moderator and ESG Score as independent variable which is not statistically significant the F value are 3,14 is 1.004 and the p value is 0.42 with a small partial eta squared $\eta^2p = 0.177$ indicating a weak effect size. The individual contribution of ownership structure is also statistically insignificant ($F(2,14) = 1.484, p = 0.26$), with a similarly low η^2p of 0.175. Moreover the ESG Score by itself does not significantly affect the dependent variable F value 1,14 is 0.369 and the p value is 0.553 with a very low effect size η^2p is 0.026 which reinforces on the minimal influence of ESG performance when considered in isolation. The fixed effects estimates further support these findings intercept is statistically significant Estimate is 1.0204 the p value is < 0.001, which sets the baseline value of the dependent variable. However, the two ownership dummy variables, OWNERSHIP1 and OWNERSHIP2, both show negative estimates (-0.7833 and -0.3842, respectively) but are not statistically significant ($p = 0.145$ and $p = 0.273$). This suggests that different ownership categories do not have a strong or reliable influence on the outcome variable. Likewise, the ESG Score has a negative estimate of -0.0251 and is also statistically insignificant ($p = 0.553$), with a wide confidence interval (-0.114 to 0.0635), indicating considerable uncertainty in its effect.

Table no 3.8

	OWNERSHIP	Environment Score	Social Score	Governance Score	ESG Score	ROA	ROE
Mean	1	59.3	60.6	74	65.6	1.33	13.2
	2	63	58	68	64	0.59	5.44
	0	52.8	63.2	63	59.7	1.1	13.8

The comparative analysis of ownership types reveals distinct variations in ESG performance and financial metrics such as Return on Assets and Return on Equity. Ownership type 1 that is of private banks shows that the highest overall ESG performance, with the highest Environment Score 59.3 Social Score 60.6 Governance Score 74 and ESG combined Score 65.6. This ownership type 2 that is public sector banks also shows relatively strong financial performance, with a ROA of 1.33 and a ROE of 13.2. In contrast, ownership type 2 demonstrates a slightly better Environmental Score 63 but lower Social 58 and Governance Scores 68 resulting in a slightly lower ESG Score of 64. However, it reports the weakest financial performance among the three groups, with a ROA of just 0.59 and ROE of 5.44. Ownership type 0, despite having the lowest ESG Score (59.7), shows competitive financial results with a ROA of 1.1 and the highest ROE of 13.8.

These patterns suggest that while ownership type 1 that is private banks shows strong ESG alignment and decent financial performance, the relationship between ESG scores and financial metrics is not linear or consistent across ownership types. This calls for a deeper investigation into the role of contextual factors and long-term versus short-term effects of ESG implementation under different ownership structures.

IV FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

4.1 Enhancing ESG Integration and Strategic Alignment findings underscore the need for Indian banks to adopt a more comprehensive and integrated ESG strategy. While environmental and governance components shows that relative maturity there is a clear opportunity to increase the efforts in green finance, emissions reduction and energy efficient banking operations. Strong governance practices already a relative strength should be further institutionalized to enhance transparency, particularly through improved investor relations and stakeholder communication. The social score remains content which ensures overall holistic ESG alignment of banks expand initiatives related to employee welfare, workplace diversity, community engagement and financial literacy programs. The incorporation of ESG into risk management frameworks will definitely help in the

regulatory compliance to improve institutional resilience against systemic and reputational risks, as supported by studies such as (Giese et al.2019) and (Khan et al.2016).

4.2 Improving ESG Disclosure and Reporting Mechanisms A recurring limitation identified in the empirical analysis is the variation in ESG disclosure quality. To address this issue Indian banks should improve their reporting practices with international standards such as the Global Reporting Initiative, Sustainability Accounting Standards Board and the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures. Reporting separating environmental, social, and governance scores are recommended over combined ESG score to ensure great transparency.

In addition, the adoption of non-financial Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is essential for capturing ESG outcomes beyond profitability. Metrics related to carbon footprint, board diversity, community impact, and responsible lending can offer stakeholders a more comprehensive assessment of ESG maturity.

4.3 Interpreting ESG–Financial Performance Linkages with Caution :-The study contributes the strong short-term conclusions about the positive financial impact of ESG performance, particularly on return on assets and return on equity. While ESG may contribute to long-term financial stability and risk mitigation, overstating immediate benefits risks promoting compliance rather than short term period analysis. Future empirical models should add control variables like factors such as bank size, leverage, capital adequacy and macroeconomic volatility. Expanding the sample size and extending the period would also enhance statistical improvements and allow better identification of long-term ESG effects. This is in line with methodological recommendations found in Friede et al. (2015) and Fatemi et al. (2018).

4.4 Ownership-Specific ESG Strategy Development

The impact and implementation of ESG initiatives differ based on the ownership structure of banks. Public sector banks with their social mandates should prioritize inclusive finance, rural outreach, and development-oriented. Private sector banks in contrast can position ESG as a competitive differentiator to attract ESG-conscious investors and institutional clients. Governance frameworks must also be reviewed across ownership categories especially where ESG integration remains still compliance-driven to tracking long-term outcomes of ESG programs of both financial and non-financial is very much essential to validate whether current initiatives contribute to risk mitigation, stakeholder trust, and reputational capital.

V. FUTURE STUDIES

To strengthen future investigations into the ESG–financial performance relationship in Indian banks, several research directions are proposed. First, panel data methodologies such as fixed effects, random effects, or dynamic GMM should be employed to uncover causal linkages, incorporating lagged ESG variables to capture delayed financial impacts. Broader financial indicators beyond ROA, such as ROE, EPS, NIM, cost of capital and Tobin's Q must be considered to gain a holistic view of ESG's financial implications the role of control variables and mediators such as ownership structure, digital adoption and regulatory frameworks should be tested to understand contextual dependencies. Structural Equation Modeling can help uncover direct and indirect pathways between ESG dimensions and performance such as governance improving financial efficiency via better operational controls. Ownership and sectoral comparisons across public/private, large/small, and domestic/foreign banks may reveal heterogeneity in ESG effectiveness. Researchers should also explore non-linear and threshold effects by incorporating interaction terms, for example, between ESG scores and bank size or ownership. Qualitative methods such as case studies and stakeholder interviews would be valuable in explaining how ESG practices are interpreted and implemented—especially in underperforming areas like the Social pillar. Longitudinal studies using multi-year datasets are essential for identifying whether ESG efforts lead to sustainable improvements in stock performance, asset quality, or reputational capital. Furthermore, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in ESG analytics offers promising avenues for improving data quality, compliance monitoring, and decision-making. Lastly, cross-sector and international comparisons would provide perspective on whether ESG-finance relationships are industry-specific or structurally embedded.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study gives the insights on the evolving relationship between ESG performance and financial performance of private and public Indian banking sector. Despite increasing regulatory attention and institutional efforts, the analysis reveals that ESG factors particularly when assessed in the short term do not exhibit statistically

significant impacts on core financial indicators like Return on Assets ROA and ROE Governance emerges as the most mature ESG pillar among Indian banks, whereas the social dimension remains underdeveloped. The findings caution against overestimating the sudden financial benefits of ESG integration and instead of its potential role in long-term risk mitigation, stakeholder trust, and institutional resilience. Furthermore, the study underscores the importance of disaggregating ESG reporting, expanding beyond traditional profitability metrics, and employing advanced analytical models including panel regression and structural equation modeling to capture delayed and indirect effects. Ownership structure also plays an important role in suggesting that ESG strategies should be customized to institutional contexts with public sector banks concentrating on inclusivity and private banks leveraging ESG for differentiation. The conclusions drawn emphasize that ESG should not be viewed merely as a compliance requirement but as a strategic tool that aligns sustainable banking practices with long-term value creation. Future research that incorporates longitudinal data, AI-driven ESG analytics, and cross-sector benchmarks will be essential to unlock the full potential of ESG as a catalyst for sustainable finance in emerging economies like India.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Aldieri, L., Amendola, A., & Candila, V. (2023). The Impact of ESG Scores on Risk Market Performance. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097183>
- [2] Antunes, J., Wanke, P., Fonseca, T., & Tan, Y. (2023). Do ESG Risk Scores Influence Financial Distress? Evidence from a Dynamic NDEA Approach. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097560>
- [3] Aras, G., & Hacioglu Kazak, E. (2022). Enhancing Firm Value through the Lens of ESG Materiality: Evidence from the Banking Sector in OECD Countries. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215302>
- [4] Arribas, I., Espinós-Vañó, M. D., García, F., & Morales-Bañuelos, P. B. (2019). The inclusion of socially irresponsible companies in sustainable stock indices. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11072047>
- [5] Badía, G., Pina, V., & Torres, L. (2019). Financial performance of government bond portfolios based on environmental, social and governance criteria. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11092514>
- [6] Beisland, L. A., Zamore, S., & Mersland, R. (2023). Does It Pay to be Green? A Study of the Global Microfinance Industry. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 52(3), 631–653. <https://doi.org/10.1177/08997640221110209>
- [7] Benetyte, R., Gonenc, H., & Krusinskas, R. (2021). Corporate governance vs. Financial performance for intensity of innovation investments. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095014>
- [8] Benvenuto, M., Avram, R. L., Avram, A., & Viola, C. (2021). Assessing the impact of corporate governance index on financial performance in the Romanian and Italian banking systems. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105535>
- [9] Bilbao-Terol, A., Arenas-Parra, M., Quiroga-García, R., & Bilbao-Terol, C. (2024). Is investing in the renewable energy stock market both financially and ESG efficient? A COVID-19 pandemic analysis. *Review of Managerial Science*, 18(7), 1885–1916. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-023-00664-7>
- [10] Boateng, A., Lew, B., & Liu, Y. (2025). Corporate Social Responsibility Expenditures and Bank Performance: Role of Size Among Listed Banks in Ghana. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 18(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm18030127>
- [11] Boulhaga, M., Bouri, A., Elamer, A. A., & Ibrahim, B. A. (2023). Environmental, social and governance ratings and firm performance: The moderating role of internal control quality. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 30(1), 134–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2343>
- [12] Cantero-Saiz, M., Polizzi, S., & Scannella, E. (2024). ESG and asset quality in the banking industry: The moderating role of financial performance. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2024.102221>
- [13] Cao, J., Titman, S., Zhan, X., Zhang, W., Thank, W., Agrawal, V., Bessembinder, H., Carpenter, J., Chordia, T., Da, Z., Goyal, A., Hadlock, C., Han, B., Hartzmark, S., Hou, K., Ince, O., Jiang, H., John, K., Kaiser, L., ... Yermack, D. (2020a). NBER WORKING PAPER SERIES ESG PREFERENCE, INSTITUTIONAL TRADING, AND STOCK RETURN PATTERNS. <http://www.nber.org/papers/w28156>
- [14] Cao, J., Titman, S., Zhan, X., Zhang, W., Thank, W., Agrawal, V., Bessembinder, H., Carpenter, J., Chordia, T., Da, Z., Goyal, A., Hadlock, C., Han, B., Hartzmark, S., Hou, K., Ince, O., Jiang, H., John, K., Kaiser, L., ...

- Yermack, D. (2020b). NBER WORKING PAPER SERIES ESG PREFERENCE, INSTITUTIONAL TRADING, AND STOCK RETURN PATTERNS. <http://www.nber.org/papers/w28156>
- [15] Chams, N., García-Blandón, J., & Hassan, K. (2021). Role reversal! financial performance as an antecedent of esg: The moderating effect of total quality management. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137026>
- [16] Chiaramonte, L., Dreassi, A., Girardone, C., & Piserà, S. (2022). Do ESG strategies enhance bank stability during financial turmoil? Evidence from Europe. *European Journal of Finance*, 28(12), 1173–1211. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1351847X.2021.1964556>
- [17] corporate-governance-ratings-one-score-two-scores-or-more-2zw8sfbch8. (n.d.).
- [18] Delmas, M. A., Etzion, D., & Nairn-Birch, N. (2013). Triangulating environmental performance: What do corporate social responsibility ratings really capture? *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 27(3), 255–267. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2012.0123>
- [19] Deng, X., & Cheng, X. (2019). Can ESG indices improve the enterprises' stock market performance?-An empirical study from China. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(17). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174765>
- [20] do-environmental-and-emission-disclosure-affect-firms-2583sgsw. (n.d.).
- [21] Dogan Basar, B., Ekşi, İ. H., & Yudaruddin, R. (2025). Is ownership structure effective in the relationship between ESG and bank performance? *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRC-10-2024-0194>
- [22] Doni, F., & Fiameni, M. (2024). Can innovation affect the relationship between Environmental, Social, and Governance issues and financial performance? Empirical evidence from the STOXX200 index. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 33(2), 546–574. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3500>
- [23] Dragomir, V. D., Bătae, O. M., Ionescu, B. Ștefan, & Ionescu-Feleagă, L. (2022). THE INFLUENCE OF ESG FACTORS ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN THE BANKING SECTOR DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC. *Economic Computation and Economic Cybernetics Studies and Research*, 56(4), 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.24818/18423264/56.4.22.05>
- [24] Economidou, C., Gounopoulos, D., Konstantios, D., & Tsiritakis, E. (2023). Is sustainability rating material to the market? *Financial Management*, 52(1), 127–179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fima.12406>
- [25] El Houry, R., Nasrallah, N., & Alareeni, B. (2023). ESG and financial performance of banks in the MENAT region: concavity–convexity patterns. *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*, 13(1), 406–430. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2021.1929807>
- [26] Ersoy, E., Swiecka, B., Grima, S., Özen, E., & Romanova, I. (2022). The Impact of ESG Scores on Bank Market Value? Evidence from the U.S. Banking Industry. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14159527>
- [27] Fernández-Miguélez, S. M., Díaz-Puche, M., Campos-Soria, J. A., & Galán-Valdivieso, F. (2020). The impact of social media on restaurant corporations' financial performance. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041646>
- [28] Gao, S., Meng, F., Wang, W., & Chen, W. (2023). Does ESG always improve corporate performance? Evidence from firm life cycle perspective. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1105077>
- [29] Gavana, G., Gottardo, P., & Moisello, A. M. (2022). Related Party Transactions and Earnings Management: The Moderating Effect of ESG Performance. Empirical Evidence from Italy. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14105823>
- [30] Gholami, A., Murray, P. A., & Sands, J. (2022). Environmental, Social, Governance & Financial Performance Disclosure for Large Firms: Is This Different for SME Firms? *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14106019>
- [31] Guidelines for Invigilators-UG Program. (n.d.).
- [32] Gull, A. A., Saeed, A., Suleman, M. T., & Mushtaq, R. (2022). Revisiting the association between environmental performance and financial performance: Does the level of environmental orientation matter? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(5), 1647–1662. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2310>
- [33] Gutiérrez-Ponce, H., & Wibowo, S. A. (2023). Do Sustainability Activities Affect the Financial Performance of Banks? The Case of Indonesian Banks. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086892>
- [34] Gutiérrez-Ponce, H., & Wibowo, S. A. (2023). Do Sustainability Activities Affect the Financial Performance of Banks? The Case of Indonesian Banks. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086892>

- [35] Hai, M., Fang, Z., & Li, Z. (2022). Does Business Group's Conscious of Social Responsibility Enhance its Investment Efficiency? Evidence from ESG Disclosure of China's Listed Companies. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084817>
- [36] Ioannou, I., & Serafeim, G. (2015). The impact of corporate social responsibility on investment recommendations: Analysts' perceptions and shifting institutional logics. *Strategic Management Journal*, 36(7), 1053–1081. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2268>
- [37] Ivascu, L., Domil, A., Sarfraz, M., Bogdan, O., Burca, V., & Pavel, C. (2022). New insights into corporate sustainability, environmental management and corporate financial performance in European Union: an application of VAR and Granger causality approach. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(55), 82827–82843. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-21642-8>
- [38] Jaiwani, M., & Gopalkrishnan, S. (2023). Do private and public sector banks respond to ESG in the same way? Some evidences from India. *Benchmarking*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-05-2023-0340>
- [39] Ji, L., Sun, Y., Liu, J., & Chiu, Y. ho. (2023). Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) and market efficiency of China's commercial banks under market competition. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(9), 24533–24552. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-23742-x>
- [40] Jung, Y. L., & Yoo, H. S. (2023). Environmental, social, and governance activities and firm performance: Global evidence and the moderating effect of market competition. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 30(6), 2830–2839. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2518>
- [41] Kempf, A., & Osthoff, P. (2007). The effect of socially responsible investing on portfolio performance. *European Financial Management*, 13(5), 908–922. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-036X.2007.00402.x>
- [42] Kim, J., & Lee, Y. (2023). Association between Earnings Announcement Behaviors and ESG Performances. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097733>
- [43] Kodirjonova, N., & Kim, J. D. (2023). Examining the Link between CSRD and FP in Korean Companies: The Moderating Effect of Company Reputation. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086986>
- [44] Kouaib, A. (2022). Corporate Sustainability Disclosure and Investment Efficiency: The Saudi Arabian Context. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142113984>
- [45] la Torre, M., Leo, S., & Panetta, I. C. (2021). Banks and environmental, social and governance drivers: Follow the market or the authorities? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(6), 1620–1634. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2132>
- [46] Landi, G. C., Iandolo, F., Renzi, A., & Rey, A. (2022). Embedding sustainability in risk management: The impact of environmental, social, and governance ratings on corporate financial risk. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(4), 1096–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2256>
- [47] Lee, E. (2020). Environmental Regulation and Financial Performance in China: An Integrated View of the Porter Hypothesis and Institutional Theory. *Sustainability*, 12(23), 10183. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su122310183>
- [48] Li, T., Trinh, V. Q., & Elnahass, M. (2023). Drivers of Global Banking Stability in Times of Crisis: The Role of Corporate Social Responsibility. *British Journal of Management*, 34(2), 595–622. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.12631>
- [49] Li, Z., Feng, L., Pan, Z., & Sohail, H. M. (2022). ESG performance and stock prices: evidence from the COVID-19 outbreak in China. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01259-5>
- [50] Lisin, A., Kushnir, A., Koryakov, A. G., Fomenko, N., & Shchukina, T. (2022). Financial Stability in Companies with High ESG Scores: Evidence from North America Using the Ohlson O-Score. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010479>
- [51] Liu, H., Wu, K., & Zhou, Q. (2022). Whether and How ESG Impacts on Corporate Financial Performance in the Yangtze River Delta of China. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(24). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416584>
- [52] Liu, X., Dong, J., Ji, K., Li, X., & Xu, S. (2022). Investigating the 'Short Pain' and 'Long Gain' Effect of Environmental Regulation on Financial Performance: Evidence from Chinese Listed Polluting Firms. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042412>
- [53] Liu, Y., Kim, C. Y., Lee, E. H., & Yoo, J. W. (2022). Relationship between Sustainable Management Activities and Financial Performance: Mediating Effects of Non-Financial Performance and Moderating Effects of Institutional Environment. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031168>
- [54] Luo, X., Wang, H., Raithel, S., & Zheng, Q. (2015). Corporate social performance, analyst stock recommendations, and firm future returns. In *Strategic Management Journal* (Vol. 36, Issue 1, pp. 123–136). John Wiley and Sons Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2219>

- [55] Lupu, I., Hurduzeu, G., & Lupu, R. (2022). How Is the ESG Reflected in European Financial Stability? Sustainability (Switzerland), 14(16). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141610287>
- [56] Maztoul, S. (2025). BANKS' SUSTAINABILITY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: THE ROLE OF CREDIT RISK. Financial and Credit Activity: Problems of Theory and Practice, 2(61), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcapt.2.61.2025.4647>
- [57] Mensah, L., & Bein, M. A. (2023). Sound Corporate Governance and Financial Performance: Is There a Link? Evidence from Manufacturing Companies in South Africa, Nigeria, and Ghana. Sustainability (Switzerland), 15(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15129263>
- [58] Moskovics, P., Wanke, P., Tan, Y., & Gerged, A. M. (2024). Market structure, ESG performance, and corporate efficiency: Insights from Brazilian publicly traded companies. Business Strategy and the Environment, 33(2), 241–262. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3492>
- [59] Nguyen, T. H. H., Elmagrhi, M. H., Ntim, C. G., & Wu, Y. (2021). Environmental performance, sustainability, governance and financial performance: Evidence from heavily polluting industries in China. Business Strategy and the Environment, 30(5), 2313–2331. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2748>
- [60] Park, B. J. (2021). Corporate social and financial performance: the role of firm life cycle in business groups. Sustainability (Switzerland), 13(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13137445>
- [61] Pereira, C., Monteiro, A., Silva, D., & Lima, A. (2023). Do the Levels of Environmental Sustainability Disclosure and Indebtness Affect the Quality of Earnings? Sustainability (Switzerland) , 15(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15042871>
- [62] Pham, T. N., Tran, P. P., Le, M. H., Vo, H. N., Pham, C. D., & Nguyen, H. D. (2022). The Effects of ESG Combined Score on Business Performance of Enterprises in the Transportation Industry. Sustainability (Switzerland), 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148354>
- [63] Piao, X., Xie, J., & Managi, S. (2022). Environmental, social, and corporate governance activities with employee psychological well-being improvement. BMC Public Health, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12350-y>
- [64] Prasad, R., & Mondal, A. (2025). Nexus between ESG scores and financial performance: evidence from the Indian banking sector. Asian Journal of Accounting Research. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-06-2024-0244>
- [65] Raza, H., Khan, M. A., Mazliham, M. S., Alam, M. M., Aman, N., & Abbas, K. (2022). Applying artificial intelligence techniques for predicting the environment, social, and governance (ESG) pillar score based on balance sheet and income statement data: A case of non-financial companies of USA, UK, and Germany. Frontiers in Environmental Science, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.975487>
- [66] Rodionova, M., Skhvediani, A., & Kudryavtseva, T. (2022). ESG as a Booster for Logistics Stock Returns—Evidence from the US Stock Market. Sustainability (Switzerland), 14(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912356>
- [67] Sandberg, H., Alnoor, A., & Tiberius, V. (2023). Environmental, social, and governance ratings and financial performance: Evidence from the European food industry. Business Strategy and the Environment, 32(4), 2471–2489. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.3259>
- [68] Scholtens, B., & van't Klooster, S. (2019). Sustainability and bank risk. Palgrave Communications, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0315-9>
- [69] Siminica, M., Cristea, M., Sichigea, M., Noja, G. G., & Anghel, I. (2019). Well-governed sustainability and financial performance: A new integrative approach. Sustainability (Switzerland), 11(17). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11174562>
- [70] Teng, X., Ge, Y., Wu, K. S., Chang, B. G., Kuo, L., & Zhang, X. (2022). Too little or too much? Exploring the inverted U-shaped nexus between voluntary environmental, social and governance and corporate financial performance. Frontiers in Environmental Science, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.969721>
- [71] Thomas, J., Yao, W., Zhang, F., & Zhu, W. (2022). Meet, beat, and pollute. Review of Accounting Studies, 27(3), 1038–1078. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11142-022-09694-0>
- [72] Velte, P. (2021). Environmental performance, carbon performance and earnings management: Empirical evidence for the European capital market. Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, 28(1), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2030>
- [73] Waddock, S. A., & Graves, S. B. (1997). The corporate social performance-financial performance link. Strategic Management Journal, 18(4), 303–319. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-0266\(199704\)18:4<303::AID-SMJ869>3.0.CO;2-G](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199704)18:4<303::AID-SMJ869>3.0.CO;2-G)
- [74] Xie, Y., Fang, Y., & Zhang, D. (2022). How Environmental Performance Affects Financial Performance in the Food Industry: A Global Outlook. Sustainability (Switzerland), 14(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042127>

- [75] Xu, X., & Liu, Z. (2023). ESG, Cultural Distance and Corporate Profitability: Evidence from Chinese Multinationals. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15086771>
- [76] Yeomans, J. S. (2004). Rating and Evaluating the Combined Financial and Environmental Performance of Companies in the Metals and Mining Sector. In *Journal of Environmental Informatics* (Vol. 3, Issue 2). www.iseis.org/jei
- [77] Yoo, S., Eom, J., & Han, I. (2020). Too costly to disregard: The cost competitiveness of environmental operating practices. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12155971>
- [78] Zhao, S., & Zhao, Y. (2023). Corporate Sustainable Development from the Perspective of the Effect of Institutional Investors' Shareholding on Earnings Management. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021281>
- [79] Zheng, J., Khurram, M. U., & Chen, L. (2022). Can Green Innovation Affect ESG Ratings and Financial Performance? Evidence from Chinese GEM Listed Companies. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148677>